

Supplementary Figures

Figure 1

Sobol Sensitivity S1,ST (Low NRG Stimulation)

Casein mRNA Sensitivity

Casein mRNA Sensitivity

Transcription Delay Sensitivity

Transcription Delay Sensitivity

Time-dependent Switch Sensitivity

Time-dependent Switch Sensitivity

Figure 2

Sobol Sensitivity S1,ST (High NRG Stimulation)

Casein mRNA Sensitivity

Casein mRNA Sensitivity

Transcription Delay Sensitivity

Transcription Delay Sensitivity

Time-dependent Switch Sensitivity

Time-dependent Switch Sensitivity

Figure 5

Initial HER2 (Low)

Initial HER2 (Medium/Base)

Initial HER2 (High)

Figure 6

Initial HER4 (Low)

Initial HER4 (Medium/Base)

Initial HER4 (High)

Figure 7

Initial JAK (Low)

Initial JAK (Medium/Base)

Initial JAK (High)

Figure 8

Initial PPN (Low)

Initial PPN (Medium/Base)

Initial PPN (High)

Figure 9

Initial PPX (Low)

Initial PPX (Medium/Base)

Initial PPX (High)

Figure 10

Transcription Hill-Coefficient (0.5)

Transcription Hill-Coefficient (1.0)

Transcription Hill-Coefficient (1.5)

Figure 11

STAT Dimer Nuclear Translocation (Low)

STAT Dimer Nuclear Translocation (medium)

STAT Dimer Nuclear Translocation (High)

Figure 12

HER4 Constitutive Homodimerization (Low)

HER4 Constitutive Homodimerization (Medium/Baseline)

HER4 Constitutive Homodimerization (High)

Figure 13

HER4-HER2 Heterodimerization (Low)

HER4-HER2 Heterodimerization (Medium)

HER4-HER2 Heterodimerization (High)

Figure 14

HER4 JAK-Independent Activation (Low)

HER4 JAK-Independent Activation (Medium)

HER4 JAK-Independent Activation (High)

Supplementary Figure Captions

Figure 1: Sobol first order (S1) and total effect sensitivities (ST) for the HER4-JAK-STAT model at low (1 nM) NRG stimulations.

Figure 2: Sobol first order (S1) and total effect sensitivities (ST) for the HER4-JAK-STAT model at high (20 nM) NRG stimulations.

In these plots, we mostly see the same set of species and parameters as the NRG stimulation used (10 nM) in the main section. One difference is observed in the transcription delay where more effect of the transport rates is seen at 10 nM than at low NRG.

Figure 5-10: Parameter sweep plots for three different initial concentrations (low, nominal and high) of different species in the model. The low and high bounds were obtained by applying fixed percentages (15-20%) on the nominal set of values. Both time-integrated and instantaneous time profiles are shown. Species like HER2 and HER4 which were observed to be highly sensitive before were seen to alter the time profiles at different ligand stimulations drastically. They also influenced the time-dependent switching behavior by shifting both the peak mRNA values and also the times of transition.

Figure 11-14: Parameter sweep plots for three values (low, nominal and high) of different reactions in the model. The low and high bounds were obtained by applying fixed percentages (15-20%) on the nominal set of values. Both time-integrated and instantaneous time profiles are shown. The transcription Hill-coefficient greatly influenced both overall dynamics of transcription the switching behavior. The HER4 heterodimerization rates also changed the late time dynamics and transition times. These reactions show why HER4 and HER2 initial numbers were also sensitizing. Much of the influence of these receptors came through these dimerization reactions. The nuclear translocation rate of STAT5 dimer like mRNA export rate shown in figures in the main text influenced the delay and timing of switch. Finally, the JAK-independent HER4 activation also changed the late time behavior. At low activation, it produced a steady level of activation in 24-48 hour period while at high levels of activation it produced a substantial increase in the late stages.